

Catalytic Studies on Nickel-Mordenite*

S. NARAYANAN

Indian Institute of Petroleum, Dehra Dun (U.P.)

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Molecular sieve zeolites are becoming increasingly important as catalysts for several major refining and petrochemical processes because of their structural features. These features are extensive interlattice pore volume, a pore size of molecular dimension, a large population of exchangeable cations within the interlattice pore volume. Mordenite zeolites are unique because of their two dimensional tubular structure, high stability and high selectivity for molecules of dimension 5.81×6.95 Å.

Nickel-mordenite catalyst was prepared from sodium mordenite by ion exchange so as to get a good dispersion. Hydrogenation of benzene and dehydrogenation of cyclohexane were carried out on the reduced catalyst at different temperatures and hydrogen partial pressures. Turnover numbers and activation energies were calculated. The activities of nickel catalysts are compared. ESR studies were also made on mordenite catalysts.

MOLECULAR sieves are important as catalysts and as supports in petroleum and petrochemical industries due to their crystalline structure, definite pore size, large polar surface and remarkable thermal stability. Mordenite has a definite advantage over other zeolites because of its two dimensional pore structure and high silica-alumina ratio which is responsible for its thermal stability and sometimes higher catalytic activity. Particularly, the synthetic mordenites are free of stacking faults and are highly active for hydrocracking, hydroisomerization, alkylation, reforming and cracking-reactions which proceed through carbo-nium ion intermediates^{1,2}.

Catalytic sites are thought to be located at the cation sites or sites vacated by cations. Different cations can affect the catalytic properties of mordenite differently. In the present work a nickel-mordenite catalyst prepared from sodium mordenite by ion exchange which gives almost atomic dispersion of the metal, was used³.

Hydrogenation of benzene and dehydrogenation of cyclohexane were selected as model reactions in characterizing the activity of nickel-mordenite catalyst because of the simplicity of reaction and the product formed could be easily analyzed and could directly be correlated with the activity of the catalyst.

ESR studies were also made on the mordenite catalyst to get an idea of the nature and the environment of the metal, atom in the catalyst.

Experimental

Sodium mordenite, Alite 150, 1.8 mm (lot 1695) extrudates supplied by L' Air Liquide, Paris was

used. Fig. 1 gives the schematic diagram showing the formation of nickel-mordenite from sodium mordenite by ion exchange. Sodium mordenite was converted to its ammonium form by refluxing with aqueous ammonium nitrate at 90°. The ammonium mordenite thus formed is refluxed with nickel nitrate solution at 90°. The catalyst was washed well with water and dried at 110°. Nickel in the catalyst, estimated by atomic absorption spectroscopy, was found to be 0.5%. The sodium content was estimated by flame photometry (0.75%). The catalyst was reduced in flowing hydrogen (70 ml/min) at 400° for 6 hours.

A vertical tubular glass reactor was used. Reduced catalyst was crushed and only catalysts of mesh size 10-12 were used. Before each experiment the catalyst was reduced in flowing hydrogen at 400° for one hour. The products were analyzed by gas chromatography.

Fig. 1. Schematic diagram of cation exchange on mordenite.

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Benzene hydrogenation was carried out in the temperature region 90-200° at LHSV of 1.5 and 3.0 and at hydrogen/benzene mole ratios of 6.3 and 4.6 respectively. Turnover numbers were calculated for each experiment and the results are tabulated (Table 1). The dehydrogenation of cyclohexane was carried out in the temperature region 180-300° at LHSV 1.5, and at hydrogen/cyclohexane mole ratio of 7.6 (Table 2). Turnover number is defined as the number of cyclohexane molecules formed from benzene or the benzene molecules formed from cyclohexane per second per exposed atom of nickel.

A Varian E4 ESR spectrometer was used. The 'g' values were determined using DPPH as a calibrant ($g=2.0036$).

TABLE 1—HYDROGENATION OF BENZENE ON NICKEL-MORDENITE

Temp. °C	LHSV	Hydrogen/benzene mole ratio	Turnover Number $\times 10^{-5}$
90	3.0	4.6	8
110	3.0	4.6	11
130	3.0	4.6	14
160	1.5	6.3	24
200	1.5	6.3	30

TABLE 2—DEHYDROGENATION OF CYCLOHEXANE ON NICKEL-MORDENITE

Temp. °C	Turnover Number $\times 10^{-5}$
200	63.8
240	70.7
280	202.7

LHSV : 1.5
Hydrogen/cyclohexane mole ratio : 7.6

Results and Discussion

From Tables 1 and 2, one can see that the turnover number, which gives an idea of the specific catalytic activity, generally increases with temperature. However, there is a three fold increase in the turnover number for cyclohexane dehydrogenation at 280° compared to at 240°. This may be due to the availability of a larger metal surface for the reaction due to better activation at higher temperature in presence of atomic hydrogen produced during the dehydrogenation reaction itself.

The activation energies for benzene hydrogenation and cyclohexane dehydrogenation are 3.6 and 13.8 Kcals/mole respectively, in the temperature regions studied. The low activation energy for benzene hydrogenation suggests that the reaction is a diffusion controlled one. Since the feed rate is high (LHSV = 3) and hydrogen/benzene mole ratio

is also high (4.6), it may not be the bulk diffusion which is rate controlling. Either the intraparticle or the intrapore diffusion could be the rate determining step. Because the particle size is small enough it is likely that the intrapore diffusion is the rate controlling process.

In the metal loaded zeolite catalysts, by ion exchange, the metal is expected to be dispersed well inside the cavities⁴. For a given reaction to take place the sorbate molecule has to get into the pore so as to get in contact with the metal responsible for hydrogenation and dehydrogenation. Whether a sorbate molecule can enter a mordenite pore (5.81 \times 6.95 Å) depends on its critical dimension (smallest projected diameter). Benzene with a critical diameter of 6.8 Å is just about the right size and can diffuse slowly into the mordenite cavity. The slow diffusion process may be the rate controlling step for benzene hydrogenation. Whereas, cyclohexane (critical diameter 6.1 Å) which is smaller than benzene, and the diffusion process may not be the rate controlling one. The reaction step could be the rate controlling one ; hence the higher activation energy.

In the Table 3 a nickel-silica-alumina catalyst* and the nickel-mordenite catalyst are compared for their catalytic activities. Nickel loading in silica-alumina catalyst was also done by ion exchange⁵. Eventhough, the nickel content in nickel-silica-alumina (2.2%) is higher than in nickel-mordenite (0.5%), there is a notable difference both in hydrogenation and dehydrogenation activities. May be, there are higher number of active sites present in nickel-mordenite than in the nickel-silica-alumina which is due to a better dispersion ability of mordenite compared to the amorphous silica-alumina. The absence of methyl cyclopentane as one of the

TABLE 3—COMPARISON OF THE ACTIVITIES OF NICKEL SILICA-ALUMINA AND NICKEL-MORDENITE

Catalyst	Temp. °C	Hydrogen/hydrocarbon mole ratio	Turnover Number $\times 10^{-5}$
<i>Benzene hydrogenation</i>			
NiSA	170	10	9.5*
NiSA	200	10	3.8*
NiM	160	6.3	24.0
NiM	200	6.3	30.0
<i>Cyclohexane dehydrogenation</i>			
NiSA	290	10	46.0*
NiM	280	7.6	202.0

(*) Calculated from Ref. (5)
Weight percentage of nickel in NiSA : 2.2
Weight percentage of nickel in NiM : 0.5

products of catalytic reaction over nickel-mordenite is probably due to the presence of higher amount of sodium (0.75% by weight). Thus by varying the level of sodium content the selectivity of the nickel-mordenite catalyst for hydrogenation or dehydrogenation/isomerization can be controlled.

TABLE 4—SUMMARY OF ESR STUDIES ON MORDENITE CATALYSTS

Catalyst	g ₁	g ₂	Intensity Relative		Peak width (G)	
			Ratio ₁	Ratio ₂	1	2
1	-	2.38	-	3	-	1460
2	-	2.38	-	3	-	1400
3	2.19	-	9	-	-	410
4	2.28	2.48	42	27	680	1760
5	2.21	2.58	10	19	360	1200

Catalysts :

1. Fresh sodium mordenite powder, evacuated at 400° for 1 hour.
2. Unreduced nickel mordenite powder, evacuated at 400° for 1 hour.
3. Used nickel mordenite, regenerated in flowing oxygen at 400° for 2 hours and 500° for 2 hours : reduced in flowing hydrogen at 400° for 4 hours, evacuated at 400° for 1 hour.
4. Regeneration and reduction as for 3, passed 1% thiophene in cyclohexane at 280°, (4.5 ml/hr) for 1 hour, evacuated at 400° for 1 hour.
5. Used nickel mordenite, reduced in hydrogen (static) at 400° for 3 hours, evacuated at 400° for 1 hour.

Fig. 2. ESR spectra of fresh sodium mordenite (1) and unreduced nickel mordenite (2)

Fig. 3. ESR spectrum of reduced nickel mordenite (3)

Fig. 4. ESR spectra of reduced nickel mordenite after 1% thiophene feed (4) and used nickel mordenite (5)

Table 4 gives the summary of ESR analysis. Fig. 2 shows the ESR spectrum of sodium mordenite (fresh) and unreduced nickel-mordenite. Both give signal, with 'g' value 2.38, which might be due to the presence of impurities such as Fe^{3+} and Mn^{2+} in mordenite itself^{6,7} or due to some trapped electrons in the cavities. Reduced nickel-mordenite gives a sharp symmetric signal (Fig. 3) and the 'g' value of 2.19 corresponds to Ni^0 reported in the literature⁸. On the other hand the used catalyst (Fig. 4) gives two signals (' g_1 '=2.21 and ' g_2 '=2.59) with broadening of peak widths. Again, the thiophene treated catalyst (Fig. 4) gives two broad signals with 'g' values 2.28 and 2.48. Assigning the 'g' values of 2.21 and 2.28 in both the cases to Ni^0 , the second broader signal may be due to partially oxidized impurities, or due to the trapped sulfur atoms, or due to the mordenite itself.

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References

1. P. B. VENUTO and P. S. LANDIS, *Advances in Catalysis*, 1968, **18**, 259.
2. J. S. BAWA, U. SHANKER and K. K. BHATTACHARYYA, *Chemical Industry Dev. Inc. CP&E*, 1974 (July).
3. J. A. RABO, V. SCHOMAKER and P. E. PICKERT, III *Intern. Congr. Catalysis*, North-Holland Pub., Amsterdam, 1965, p. 1264.
4. D. W. BRECK, *J. Chem. Educ.*, 1964, **41**, 678.
5. M. OKADA and T. SHIRASAKI, *Catalyst (Tokyo)*, 1967, **9**, 85.
6. J. TURKEVICH, F. NOZAKI and D. STAMIRIS, III *Intern. Congr. Catalysis*, North-Holland Pub., Amsterdam, 1965, p. 586.
7. P. PICHAT, J. C. VEDRINE, P. GALLEZOT and B. IMELIK, *J. Catal.*, 1974, **32**, 190.
8. P. W. SELWOOD, in 'Adsorption and Collective Paramagnetism', Academic Press, Inc., New York, 1962.